

AN APPROACH TO THE ORIGIN AND DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S AND YOUTH LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue of the origin and development of children's literature. Its scientific relevance is already present in thematic research, because this literary modality has become a fundamental part of Pedagogy and the intellectual and cognitive training of children and adolescents, receiving a special chapter in teacher training courses in the initial grades of elementary school. Its social relevance is present in the discussion it brings about the personological development of its target audience, inserted and transformed into films, series and other types of media and marketing objects. This is a bibliographical research work, discussed based on the authors' empirical knowledge on the subject and explored in order to clarify that the origin and development of children's literature have distinct histories and definitions, and are not subject to criteria of hasty and defined analyzes in sociological studies; rather, its bases of apprehension and understanding are based on anthropological studies, supported by the psychology of the unconscious. In general, studies on the origin and development of this type of literature are based on Western thought and all its delay caused by the institution of Christianity, by the Catholic Church, which took care to maintain in the most absolute state of illiteracy [almost] all western world. And, this condition is reflected in the formation of myopic researchers who cannot see beyond Europe as the center of the civilized world. This is not what is presented in this article, in which the theme is treated as a pragmatic human construction, destined for a specific purpose and which, given human phylogenetic evolution, remains alive and pulsating to this day.

Keywords: Children's and young adult literature. Pedagogy. Psychology. Ontogenetic and phylogenetic development.

INTRODUCTION

Children's literature is a category of literary texts with themes and verbal and visual language prepared according to the age range and cognitive development of the readers, particularly children and adolescents. What appears to be a simple adaptation of stories created specifically for adults to a smaller audience is a construction from the 17th century onwards; but that, in its beginnings, the entire literary construction was designed to serve children and their infinite curiosity about things.

Thus, the question arises: How did the habit of telling stories arise in the human race? It is observed that during the childhood period, children love to listen to bedtime stories. Do these stories reflect fears, learning, hopes and doubts that have not always been companions of the human species? This habit, which is as old as the existence of humanity itself, was possibly born from the need to communicate something that could have a specific and special meaning for all participants in the community and, beyond it, as something inherent to the species; from which it can be inferred that telling stories is a way of allowing the healthy development of humanity and perpetuating the knowledge that underlies civilization and social thought.

Lima (2007) presents as an argument the hypothesis that storytelling is an art that was born before history and has its most distant past in orality. Children's literature therefore arises from the art of recreating the fantasies of popular memory.

Bringing people together to listen to stories is an action that continues to this day; Listening to stories enchants and opens up different horizons of possibilities. The voice, the gestures, the performance of those who tell stories have something magical that is capable of seducing children and adults and this magic, which is a specific characteristic of the human being, cannot be, in any way, replaced by the various technologies existing in contemporary times.

The stories, fables, legends, poetry and the various types of text that are part of the universe that is conventionally called *Classic Children's and Youth Literature* have their origins in the popular novels of the Middle Ages: These novels, in turn, have their origins in India. A common characteristic of novels from the Middle Ages and Indian novels is the fact that the word was attributed a magical and fantasy power. This power exists to this day; Proof of this is the fact that more and more individuals have become interested in telling and listening to stories. There are even courses that prepare storytellers, because it is not enough to know them; you

have to know intonation, plot, corporeality and vocabulary expression, tone of voice, among other reading strategies. In this regard, Solé (1998) argues that,

Reading strategies are the necessary tools for developing proficient reading. Its use allows autonomous understanding and interpretation of the texts read and aims to awaken the teacher to the importance of developing effective work towards the formation of independent, critical and reflective readers (SOLE, 1998, p. 23).

The word, as it is spoken and/or heard, has the power to build new intellectual and cognitive processes, protect and comfort those who feel insecure, threaten those who feel unattainable, build dreams and fantasies that, apparently, were distant and unattainable. It can, finally, make new worlds and realities happen in and from thought. In this narrative called *Primordial*, the words have this, at times, divinatory character; sometimes mysterious, which always seduces or enchants listeners. These characteristics, added to a background of mysterious and fabulous reality, will later be found in Eastern narratives, which already existed even in Archaic Antiquity and which were transmitted throughout the world, generation after generation, through the oral tradition that was peculiar to them. and, because there was no other way to do it.

Fernandes (2007) argues that,

State, universities, private sector and civil society organizations discuss the relationship between reading and social inclusion, linking the importance of reading to school and revealing the emergence and development of public policies that aim to improve the literacy conditions of the population (FERNANDES, 2007, p. 10).

Literature represents the maximum, in terms of splendor, that a nation can gather from its people, in an attempt to explain what it cannot do, through the means of logic. It is far beyond a fantastic collection and, given its power of fantasy and freedom to unite several elements in a single point, making them real to thought, where it is possible to circumvent existence in all its rudeness, it has It is a way of expressing the social *modus* of life, the scientific discoveries, not yet proven, and the hypotheses about all the elements that make up *Physis*.

It is conventional to classify it as a meaningless expression of delusions and abstractions in which its value would be in the aesthetic condition it presents, without ever being able to be considered as a sovereign production of knowledge, with such a *status* reserved for the so-called erudite sciences, in that complete rigor would be applied to the methodological process of

investigation and the results achieved, as if literary production did not pass through such filters of analysis, interpretation, validation and refutation.

During the period in which Christianity became institutionalized and achieved total dominance over people and their thoughts, through Catholic Doctrine, children's literature was practically banned in Europe, as it was considered lies; in other words, the term metaphor was replaced by falsehoods and this would induce children to believe in things that did not exist, disturbing the moral construction of their personological structures and character. All the molding that is said about the non-existence of a phase of childhood and adolescence in the Middle Ages is fact; however, it serves as a smokescreen to cover up all the evil that the Catholic Church has imposed on the world for centuries; One of these is the prohibition of telling stories to children. In parallel, with the emergence of the Enlightenment, stories of a children's nature returned to public appearance, being addressed, at first, to the noble adults of the Court, something like a live rehearsal and, centuries later, when schools and all the need for a broader pedagogical practice, these same stories are being told to children by teachers to their students, which culminates in the popular acceptance of Children's Literature as something to be practiced on a large scale, as it helped in the formation of childish personality.

ABOUT THE CONCEPT OF LITERATURE

Very common to hear the question: *But, what is literature?* Even though the question seems simple, and you have already read several Literature books, the answer to the concept is not that obvious. This happens, perhaps, due to the fact that there are few times when people are concerned with classifying the types of texts that they read and conceptualizing, in a global way, the field in which they focus.

Wellek and Warren, in 1942, when seeking to conceptualize Literature, in a book where they discuss the theory of literature, define it as being “everything that is found in print” (Id.). The authors themselves recognize the limitation of the concept, as technical or informative texts could be read as literary. Following the reasoning, they say that Literature is limited to 'great books, to books that, whatever their theme, are notable for their form or aesthetic expression'.

In this sense, this observation already advances the discussion a little, considering that it contains an idea of *aesthetic value*, even if it is not clear what would make the book's aesthetics notable. Finally, the authors propose that the term Literature appears more appropriate when limited to the art of literature (that is, imaginative literature). Further in the

text, they inform that there is a particular way of using language in Literature, since language is the material of literature. Thus, from Wallek and Warren's text it can be concluded that Literature implies a connotative use of language, where such a concept implies the presence of ambiguities, symbols, plurimeaning and expressivity, which will give Literature its fictional, inventive and imaginative.

Still from the perspective of dealing with concepts that allow a greater understanding of what the literary phenomenon is, the concept presented by D'Onofrio (1997) can be brought into discussion, where he argues that literature is a form of knowledge of reality that uses fiction and uses language elaborated through art as a means of expression, which makes use of metaphors, metonymies and other accessories of poetic license. This concept is quite productive and will serve as a reference throughout the study, as it, in addition to corroborating Wellek and Warren's conceptualization, expands it in the sense of including the idea of *knowledge of reality*.

Children's Literature has to do with childhood and youth; But, how did this historical type of text production, aimed at this specific audience, begin, in which an entire psychological situation needs to be taken into account, when producing the stories and their plots?

Therefore, the question, which appears to be simple, requires an answer with a good basis for elaboration. There are still controversies in the discussion of the origins of Children's Literature. Researchers are not unanimous in affirming one or another of the possible origins of this literature and it is therefore necessary to see what these aspects are and think about the way in which the two lines of thought complement each other and make studies evolve, highlighting that the election of one of them will certainly not exclude the presence of the other.

One of the aspects for understanding Children's Literature reveals that it is intrinsically linked to the emergence of bourgeois education, which means that it would be associated with textbooks and that, in these books, stories would initially have been conveyed to children. Thinking about it this way, it won't be difficult to understand the fact that it has always been associated with reading a text for childhood and adolescence and the need to learn a moralistic lesson from the story; which demonstrates that the primary objective of these stories would be to sign something to the children or to admonish them. In this sense, these texts would not be explored in terms of their particularly literary aspects, only as tools that would serve to perpetuate the values, ideologies and stances of the bourgeois class.

In this aspect, Children's Literature, due to the fact that it is seen only as a teaching instrument, is impoverished and does not allow its various psychological, unconscious and pre-conscious facets to be explored. As a result, the richness of the world and the possibility of

expanding experiences and knowledge are lost, in the name of a supposed *morality* that would be the only objective to be achieved with reading. However, the existence of this morality cannot be denied, nor even the pedagogical character that can be inferred from it. However, this character must be associated with other readings and other literary benefits, which can be achieved through Children's and Youth Literature.

Seen from another angle, Children's Literature would come from manifestations of popular tradition. The plurilingual richness, humanism, complexity and multi-significance of the structure and themes that we find within it bear witness to this characteristic. In this case, it would come from oral narratives from the 4th century and is no longer just a text whose objective would be to bring some teaching to children and prepare them for adult life, but becomes a source of pleasure and knowledge of the most varied stages of life, in addition to being an excellent means of entertainment, a source of pleasure and knowledge, providing the reader with the most diverse simulations of human relationships with their complex characteristics and a multitude of meanings.

The different peoples, with their most diverse cultures, languages, customs, have created the most wonderful and fantastic stories, the most tragic and comical situations, the most unforgettable, terrible and adorable characters that everyone comes into contact with and ends up meeting throughout their lives: life and death, as challenging elements of an explanation.

Some scholars claim that we can only talk about Children's Literature from the 17th century onwards, when the organization of teaching and the bourgeois educational system took place. These scholars state that, during this period, there was no idea of childhood like the one adopted today; children lived the lives of adults, and there were no books or stories that were specifically addressed to them: there was no what could be called Children's and *Young Adult Literature*.

By following this line of reasoning, it is possible to associate the birth of Children's Literature with the books that are published and which have children as their target audience and Pedagogy as their function. This thesis about the origin of Children's Literature is closely linked to that aspect that associates children's books with a pedagogical character, which have always conveyed a moral idea in their stories. Thus, from this point of view, the playful fictional character of Literature is not addressed and it is just an instrument to support teaching.

Denise Escarpit, in her book, *Children's and Young Adult Literature in Europe*, begins her investigative studies from the 17th century and points out what the first books for children

would have been. He cites, as an example, the work *Orbis Sensualium Pictus* (1658), by JA Comenius (1592-1670), a work created with the aim of teaching Latin through engravings.

Before the 17th century, in Escarpit's view, there was Children's Literature. Various popular expressive activities such as riddles, children's rhymes and certain word games that, according to her, would be part of the genesis of Children's and Young Adult Literature, it was only later once inserted in books intended for children that these games, games and stories would be considered as such. Children, as they did not have a life differentiated from that of adults, had an experience of all the situations characteristic of adult life. Nothing was strange to them, nothing was forbidden to them, everyone participated together in the common process of survival and everyone shared the joys and anxieties that were part of common life.

At 7 (seven) years old, the child was already an adult and participated equally in the destiny of the community, including being part of working life, as education consisted of professional training. The child was knowledgeable about all social customs, habits, language, games, games and parties; apparently, in the medieval period, there were no subjects that children were unaware of. The themes of adult life, such as joys, the struggle for survival, concerns, sexuality, death, transgression of social rules, imagery, beliefs, celebrations, indignations, perplexities were experienced by the entire community, regardless of age groups.

The fact that everyone shares all aspects of common life: all beliefs and all fears, all struggles and all achievements, makes everything seem natural, even the aspects that today are considered to be fantastic. or wonderful in the stories that were told during this period and which, in one way or another, have been transmitted to the present day. We are, then, faced with popular narratives, which have their origins in mystical narratives that have always existed in the history of humanity. These linguistic expressions bring with them an entire worldview, a whole complex tangle of traditions and knowledge translated into a fanciful and delirious imagination that allows readers and listeners, to this day, to be enchanted by the stories, tales, games, games, riddles that have survived time and have reached the present, through oral tradition.

Today, protected by a series of laws; therefore, living in a different psychological world from the world of adults, there are a series of prohibitions and strategies to protect children so that they are not directly involved in the psychological everyday life reserved for adults: there are, really, two different worlds. But, as it wasn't always like this, there is currently, in society, a preparation for adult life for issues and particularities of this other world that is that of adults.

Unlike medieval society, today there are programs and problems that are specific to each stage of life and that will not, in most cases, be shared by adults and children.

There is a persistent belief that, even if adults and children today are together listening to stories, it is always the adult who teaches something to the child, preparing them for a life to come. To the same extent, in their intrapsychic world, many ideas and doubts are brought to light, which already expresses that this passivity that is intended to be attributed to the child is not authentic. The idea of sharing experiences between adults and children, which was a type of miniature adult, a common presence in the Middle Ages, ceased to exist, at least in a formal way.

One of the most unusual beliefs of the 20th and 21st centuries is that children do not have sufficient intellectual and cognitive capacity to interpret the world and things, even in their own particular and unique way. When reading classic tales, these, in themselves, already have their formula for clarifying their intentions in relation to the reader and, in turn, he processes, in his own way, the message that is transmitted and, as he becomes cognitively mature, rereads and becomes capable of transferring this knowledge to others, not to mention that everyday situations reveal themselves as potential experiences that add value to individuals and can be compared with the situations presented in the texts.

Through reading stories, this little reader learns that the language of books has its conventions, and that words can create imaginary worlds, opening all the floodgates to understand the world through the eyes of the authors and the experiences of the characters (ABRAMOVICH, 1989 , p. 14).

Of course, not all of these characteristics will be present in all stories; but it is certainly possible to find some of them among the many stories that are heard or told to children.

These last observations have to do with the linguistic structure of the narratives. Observe its formal structure: the presence of riddles is noted: it will almost always be from a riddle that the hero will discover what to do to find the solution to a problem; this same hero and his assistant, at times, will go through quite comical and fanciful situations: as the stories unfold, metamorphoses almost always occur - a character who transforms into an animal and who, through an enchantment, regains his form human; the expectation of learning through children's stories is certain and, after all these adventures, the certainty of a happy ending.

THE EMERGENCE OF CHILDREN'S AND YOUTH LITERATURE: AN APPROACH

The entire interpretation made about children's literature is marked by the same childish rhetoric that, as there was no concept of childhood and adolescence from Antiquity until the beginning of the Modern Age, therefore there was no way for there to be a set of stories that were aimed at this group. It happens that the priestly psychological issue and its canonical rules are confused with the fact of telling stories to children, in an attempt to clarify for them the phenomena that accompany life and human existence.

It is difficult to say that literature existed in the Ancient Age, because there was not even writing and, when it emerged, it was restricted to very few individuals and to narrow regions of the globe. It was only after the Lutheran Revolution (1517) that a project began to expand schooling capacity in the West, that is, while the East had already produced and recorded an infinity of stories, Europe was still the splendid cradle of illiteracy.

But, when considering the telling of stories and their production since very archaic eras, they were initially directed at children, as soon as it was realized that their curiosity needed some mechanism to appease them, and it was not long before realizing that, sometimes, they fell asleep listening to such fantastic stories that didn't even need to be connected with situational reality. The mothers realized that their actions of telling those adventures and fantasies calmed their young children and, as ontogenetic development was the first to be observed by humans, once adults, humans missed listening to wonderful stories and, thus, feeling become calmer and more connected to their existence, which meant that the habit spread to this age group, too.

The reading and determination that is imposed at the end of the 19th Century and the beginning of the 20th Century is due to an extensive social construction, in which there is the Industrial Revolution, the birth of Sociology, intense urbanization, schooling, the emergence of Psychoanalysis bringing a new concept of man and dividing human existence into distinct phases delimited by observable psychic occurrences, which means that epistemologists tend to create a particular type of texts, with a strict language for each existential phase.

From the knowledge of the developmental phases, it became possible to categorize them and produce texts for each of them, in accordance with linguistic, intellectual and interpretation capacity. However, it is not because of categorization and psychic subdivisions that children's literature emerges; it is only placed in a pedagogical and didactic classification list, requiring

that specific methodologies for each age and psychic development stage be produced and applied to children and adolescents.

It must be clarified that children's literature was not born as an object of magic in the 20th century and it may even be that the change in thinking about the human being and its evolutionary process that took place after the publication of Charles Darwin's theory (1809-1882) on the evolution of species, in which the phylogenetic condition definitively begins to be understood, becoming an object of studies, has favored the production of a form of fantastic literature, not because of age itself; but, due to the link that modern man still maintains with his obscure and [*almost*] unknown prehistoric past, in which he was excited and amazed by natural phenomena, simply because he did not understand them.

And, when you analyze the stories and texts that are expressed in this literary modality, what you see printed in them is exactly this, everything is marked by an apparent simplicity, in which time is treated in a non-existent way, events follow a natural logic, without the glimpses of thought that mark adult literature; everything is linear in the elaboration of the act of processing information and the answers are quick and objective, leaving no room for doubts or uncertainties that cannot be clarified in a winged way.

A PRAGMATIC CLARIFICATION OF CHILDREN'S AND YOUTH LITERATURE FROM THE THOUSAND AND ONE NIGHTS

It is common to wonder why these stories have these characteristics in common. In the same way that one wonders why they have crossed the different eras and continue to enchant to this day? They talk about the simplest things that exist: love, friendship, heroism, fears, life, death, loneliness, courage, doubts, in short, they talk about the human and, more than that, they talk to the human. This is one of the reasons why children's stories are present in the development of the human personological structure. A set of stories that bring all of this are *The Thousand and One Nights*.

Itinerant commerce is one of the elements that contributed to the popularization of the tales of The Thousand and One Nights. The merchants, eager to break the monotony and tiredness of the long journeys they made, told stories along the way. Arab storytellers, around the 8th century, would have translated the Hezar Efsane and spread the stories, modifying and adapting them according to their culture, religion and language and also preserving several original elements. They would have Arabized the tales, replacing the Indian and Persian names

and places (with some exceptions) with an Arabic setting and an Islamic veneer. They would also have added a good number of stories, these typically Arabic.

It was around the year 1700 that the Frenchman Antoine Galland (1646-1715) had in his hands the manuscripts of *The Thousand and One Nights*, which he translated and published in 1704. He adapted the stories for the time and omitted the elements vulgar and erotic, replacing them with European gallantry. He added, from other manuscripts that were not part of *The Arabian Nights*, the tales of Sinbad, Aladdin and Ali Baba; This makes a difference in the number of nights in the original text.

It was with these never-ending tales at dawn that Scheherazade managed to stay alive before King Shariar, who threatened her with death. He, deceived by his first wife, swore that he would marry a virgin every night, that he would deflower her and kill her the next morning. Scheherazade then asks her father, the vizier, to let her marry the sultan. She then begs her sister to ask her to tell a story in the presence of her master. She never finishes her narratives before dawn, managing, through her cleverness, to avoid being killed thanks to the curiosity of the monarch, who wanted to know the end of the tales. At the end of a thousand and one nights, and after having had a child with her husband (or three, according to the versions), Scheherazade asks that her life be spared and is promptly granted.

This situation envelops all the other tales, night after night. But the names of Shariar and Duniazad, Sister of Scheherazade, are quickly erased in such a way that only the name of Scheherazade is mentioned when the night changes. The story of Scheherazade, which constitutes the narrative context, thus allows us to juxtapose tales that have no connection between them and that have increased the content of *The Thousand and One Nights* century after century. One of the particularities of these narratives lies in the fact that the stories are told in a nested structure. This type of literary construction is called *mise en abîme*, or construction in an abyss: a story that fits into another, into another, into another indefinitely, creating an abyss effect for those who read them. To give you a better idea of how this works, look at the label on the can of Royal powder, what do you see? A label within another label, within another label, within another label, increasingly smaller, in a sequence that tends to infinity. Another example is Russian nesting dolls: a small one inside a bigger one, inside a bigger one, inside a bigger one. In effect, the reader first encounters a narrator who reports the situation that will frame the entire context. For example, the story of Scheherazade. This, in turn, tells the king a tale, for example, the tale of the carver, the hunchback, the Jew, the steward or the Christian.

In this tale, whose center is occupied by the hunchback, she tells, one by one, the stories of the Christian tanner, the Muslim steward, the Jewish doctor and the carver, who, in turn, tells the story of a barber. The barber tells the story of each of his six brothers. This method allows Scheherazade to immortalize the narrative and keep the fatal hour at bay. This also adds diversity to the work, since each new story does not necessarily maintain a connection with the previous story, and may even have changed the narrative genre. Thus, *The Thousand and One Nights* constitute the matrix of the diverse children's stories that still enchant different generations throughout the history of humanity.

CONCLUSION

Children's literature occupies a special place in universal literature, not because of the volume of works already produced, as in Brazil there is the classic Vaga-Lume Collection, a series of books published by Editora Ática, completely aimed at this audience. This is a unique type of writing, where the characters bring together conditions from fables and classic characters, solving complex cases with great repercussions in their respective worlds; a brilliant application of psychology to literature.

Since the great classics of stories aimed at children and young people have been brought together, until 1976 there was no comprehensive study on how children's apprehension of stories worked nor how these texts interacted with them, until in this aforementioned Year, psychoanalyst Bruno Bettelheim (1903-1990) published the book *A psychoanalysis of fairy tales*, in which he presents a magnificent reading of the tales and their influence on children's cognitive and personological development. This work was joined by Marie Louise Von Franz, a Jungian psychotherapist, still in the 1970s, who brought a profound interpretation of the feelings of the characters in fairy tales and children's stories and, in the first decade of the 21st century, the book *Fadas no Divã*, authored by Brazilians Diana and Mário Corso, expanding and deepening the discussion in this field. In 2012, Brazilian author and pedagogue, Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza published the book *A Liga da Justiça no Divã*, in which he makes a profound and unprecedented study on the psychology of superheroes, characters from comic books.

The reference to these works and authors has the effect of highlighting that much more than having the work for children and young people to read, adults must know what message is transmitted through literary action; because it is not simply a story adapted to this target

audience; it brings information and a discourse that adapts to the developmental psychology age group in such a way that it leads to a very intense emotional relationship.

With the categorization of life, especially with the creation of schools and their strict division into series, according to age and cognitive development, children's literature ran the serious risk of also being departmentalized by the pedagogical establishment ; however, the person who decides what to read and the value it has and expresses must always be the reader, with adults responsible for directing the didactic work. This is because interpretations are carried out at pre-conscious and unconscious levels by the child, in a relationship of conflict and affection, according to what they face in their intrapsychic world. This was the great discovery and revelation brought to the public by the work of Bettelheim (1976) and which remains a guide to understanding children's passion for these stories.

Much is discussed about its origin and situations that favored its emergence, which appears to be an unnecessary end, because what really matters is its impact on the intellectual and personological formation of children and adolescents, with adults being responsible for developing mechanisms that enable this target audience to come into contact with children's stories.

Just like human childish feelings, children's literature is also extemporaneous, that is, it appears before any and all literature that can be known, even if it has not been registered as outside of adventure literature and religious literature. , perhaps such a decision is more of a political nature than of epistemological and pragmatic necessity.

REFERENCES

ABRAMOVICH, Fanny. *Children's Literature : Sweets and Nonsense*. 2. Ed. São Paulo: Ed. Spicione, 1997.

BETTELHEIM, Bruno. *The psychoanalysis of fairy tales*. 21. Ed. São Paulo: Paz e Terra, 2017.

CORSO, Diana L.; CORSO, Mario. *Fairies on the Divan*. Porto Alegre: Artmed, 2006.

LIMA, Adalberto. *How children's literature emerged* . (2007). Available at: <recantodasletras.uol.com.br> Accessed on: 13 Jan. 2024.

FERNANDES, Célia Regina Delácio. *Reading, children's literature and education* . Londrina: EDUEL, 2007.

SOLE, Isabel. *Reading Strategy*. Porto Alegre: Medical Arts, 1998.

SOUZA, Sérgio Rodrigues de. *The Justice League on the couch*. Mutum: Expresso Gráfica, 2012.

SOUZA, Sérgio Rodrigues de. *The Justice League on the couch*. 2. Ed. São Paulo: Perse, 2019.

TAHAN, Malba. *The one thousand and one nights*. Vol. I. São Paulo: Ediouro, 2000.

TAHAN, Malba. *The one thousand and one nights*. Vol. II. São Paulo: Ediouro, 2000.